

Design and Analysis of an Integrated Targeting System

Major Randall N. Paschall, PhD
J. R. Layne, MSEE
Wright Laboratory Avionics Directorate
WL/AAAS-3
2185 Avionics Circle
WPAFB, Ohio 45433-7301

1. ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design and analysis of integrating global positioning system (GPS), inertial navigation system (INS), and synthetic aperture radar (SAR). The intent of this research is to predict the performance of the proposed targeting system. The analysis presented here is based on a well-tuned, full-order extended Kalman filter.

The targeting aspects of the integrated INS, GPS, and SAR are investigated for both "relative" and "absolute" targeting. The simulation results indicate a theoretical possibility of obtaining absolute target position with a CEP of 10 ft.

2. INTRODUCTION

Computational capabilities of modern digital computers supports the optimal integration of data from an increased number of avionic sensors on an aircraft. Extended Kalman filters [1] are employed to integrate GPS measurements with INS data on many of today's advanced avionic systems. The success of GPS/INS integration gives insight to the integration of additional avionic sensors such as SAR. SAR is a radar capable of generating very high resolution images which can be used to designate targets. Once designated, the SAR system provides measurements related to the target's location relative to the aircraft.

This paper investigates relative and absolute targeting aspects of integrated INS, GPS, and SAR. Relative targeting refers to finding a target's location relative to the aircraft. Absolute targeting refers to finding a target's location in WGS-84 coordinates. Although it is not as accurate, absolute targeting is typically employed when the target's location is needed by someone other than the targeting aircraft (i.e. the target's coordinates are given to another aircraft).

3. SAR MEASUREMENTS

The coordinates of a Doppler processed SAR image are range and range rate. The range measurement is obtained by measuring the round-trip transit time, denoted T , of the transmitted pulse and mapping it to an equivalent range, denoted r , by use of the following relationship

$$r = \frac{c}{2}T \quad (1)$$

where c is the speed of the transmitted pulse. The range rate is found by measuring the doppler frequency shift, denoted F_d , and mapping it to an equivalent range rate, denoted \dot{r} , with the relationship

$$\dot{r} = \frac{c}{2f}F_d \quad (2)$$

where f is the frequency of the transmitted pulse.

Many SAR systems include a monopulse radar mode. The monopulse mode is used to measure the azimuth and elevation angles of the line-of-sight vector from the aircraft to the target. The azimuth angle is defined to be the angle between a vector pointing along the antenna frame y-axis and the line-of-sight vector. The elevation angle is defined to be the angle between a vector pointing along the antenna frame z-axis and the line-of-sight vector. The term monopulse refers to the ability of the radar to obtain complete angle information from a single radar pulse. In general, SAR targeting algorithms need three pieces of information to compute a target's location, namely range, Doppler cone angle, and height above the target. As shown in Figure 1, the intersection of the sphere of constant range, cone of constant range rate (centered about the aircraft velocity vector), and the plane of constant height above target defines the location of the target.

Range is measured and stored for each cell in a Doppler processed SAR image. The Doppler cone angle is obtained from the SAR range rate measurement and the INS measurement of aircraft velocity. The height above target, can be computed from the range measurement and

Figure 1: SAR Targeting Geometry

the precise angle measurements of a monopulse radar. As a final note, the coordinate systems involved in this problem are the earth centered earth fixed (ECEF) frame, the navigation frame, the heading frame, the path frame, the body frame, and the antenna frame.

4. DETERMINING TARGET LOCATION

Presented in this section are the equations needed to determine a target's location from SAR measurements. This includes the computations needed for both relative and absolute targeting. For the development which follows refer to Figure 2. It is shown in [5] that the relative target's

Figure 2: Graphical depiction of SAR targeting.

location can be determined in path frame coordinates from the following relationship.

$$p^p = \begin{bmatrix} p_x^p \\ p_y^p \\ p_z^p \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} r \left(\frac{h}{V_a} \right) \\ \left[r^2 \left(1 - \left(\frac{h}{V_a} \right)^2 \right) - \left(\tan(\eta_y) r \left(\frac{h}{V_a} \right) + \frac{h_t}{\cos(\eta_y)} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \\ \tan(\eta_y) r \left(\frac{h}{V_a} \right) + \frac{h_t}{\cos(\eta_y)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The terms $\cos(\eta_y)$ and $\tan(\eta_y)$ in Equation 3 are found using the INS indicated velocities in the following equations

$$\cos(\eta_y) = \frac{v_x^h}{v_a^h} \quad (4)$$

$$\tan(\eta_y) = \frac{-v_z^h}{v_a^h} \quad (5)$$

where v_x^h and v_z^h are the heading frame x and y components, respectively, of the aircraft velocity vector.

Given the monopulse radar measurements of azimuth and elevation angle, it is possible to compute from the following equations a unit LOS vector, $u_p^a = [u_{px}^a, u_{py}^a, u_{pz}^a]^T$, to the target in antenna coordinates.

$$u_{px}^a = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2(A) - \cos^2(E)} \quad (6)$$

$$u_{py}^a = \cos^2(A) \quad (7)$$

$$u_{pz}^a = \cos^2(E) \quad (8)$$

Notice that the vector u_p^a is a unit vector. Consequently, the components of u_p^a are direction cosine angles (i.e. the cosine of the angles between the navigation frame coordinate axes and the line of sight vector). Using this fact the height above target is given by

$$h_t = r u_{pz}^a = r \cos(\phi) \quad (9)$$

where u_{pz}^a is the z -component of u_p^a .

Once the target's relative position is found using the method described above, the target's absolute location can be determined. The relationship between the relative target position vector p^e , the target position vector r_t^e , and the aircraft position vector r_a^e in ECEF coordinates is given by

$$r_t^e = r_a^e + p^e = r_a^e + C_p^e p^p \quad (10)$$

where C_p^e is the transformation matrix from path frame to earth frame coordinates. Hence, the absolute target location can be computed from the relative target location and the aircraft position provided by the INS. An alternative scheme is given by Burgett in [6].

5. TRUTH MODELS

Presented in this section are the stochastic error models for both *indicated* and *measured* quantities. The indicated quantities include the INS position, INS velocity, INS attitude, antenna attitude, and the target location. The term *indicated* is used to denote the fact that these quantities are not processed as measurements in the Kalman filter. Instead they are used to generate a filter based estimate of the measured quantities. The symbol “ \sim ” is used over variable names to denote indicated quantities.

The measured quantities include the GPS measurements of pseudo-range and delta-range and the SAR measurement of range, range-rate, azimuth angle, and elevation angle. The symbol “ \sim ” is used over variable names to denote measured quantities.

The truth model for the INS is described in [7]. It contains 48 states and includes stochastic models for the INS aircraft position error vector, denoted δr_a^n , aircraft velocity error vector, denoted δv_a^n , the aircraft attitude error vector, denoted $\psi = [\psi_x \ \psi_y \ \psi_z]^T$, and a number of gyro and accelerometer errors. Hence, the aircraft indicated position, denoted \tilde{r}_a^n , and indicated velocity, denoted \tilde{v}_a^n , are described by the sum of the true value and the error, i.e.

$$\tilde{r}_a^n = r_a^n + \delta r_a^n, \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{v}_a^n = v_a^n + \delta v_a^n, \quad (12)$$

where r_a^n and v_a^n are the true position and velocity, respectively. The INS indicated aircraft attitude is characterized by the coordinate transformation from body to navigation frame. This indicated coordinate transformation matrix, denoted \tilde{C}_b^n , is given by the following equation

$$\tilde{C}_b^n = [I - \Psi] C_b^n \quad (13)$$

where C_b^n is the true coordinate transformation matrix, I is an identity matrix, and Ψ is the skew symmetric matrix for the vector ψ .

The antenna attitude error, denoted $\beta = [\beta_x \ \beta_y \ \beta_z]^T$, is modeled as a random bias vector with an RMS value of 1 mrad for each component. Similar to the aircraft attitude, the antenna attitude is characterized by the coordinate transformation matrix from antenna frame to body frame. This indicated coordinate transformation, denoted \tilde{C}_a^b , is characterized by the following equation

$$\tilde{C}_a^b = [I - B] C_a^b \quad (14)$$

where C_a^b is the true coordinate transformation matrix and B is the skew symmetric matrix of β .

The indicated target location, denoted \tilde{r}_t^c , is a computation of the target's location in ECEF coordinates. When

performing navigation updates its value is initialized from *a priori* knowledge of the target's location (usually obtained from a manual survey). When targeting on “target's of opportunity”, the indicated target location is initialized from the computed relative target location, p^p obtained from the first set of SAR measurements, and the INS indicated aircraft position (i.e. $\tilde{r}_t^c = C_n^e r_a^n + C_p^e p^p$ where C_n^e is the navigation to earth frame coordinate transformation and C_p^e is the path to earth frame coordinate transformation). The indicated target location vector is modeled as the sum of the true target location, denoted r_t^c , and the indicated target location error, denoted δr_t^c .

$$\tilde{r}_t^c = r_t^c + \delta r_t^c \quad (15)$$

For stationary target's (which we assume), the target's location error vector in ECEF coordinates is modeled as a random bias.

Measurement Models

Table 1 summarizes the stochastic truth models for the errors contained in both SAR and GPS measurements. Measurements from SAR and GPS are modeled as the sum of the true value and the measurement errors. Hence, SAR measurements of range, denoted \tilde{z}_r , and range rate, denoted $\tilde{z}_{\dot{r}}$, are modeled by the following equations

$$\tilde{z}_r = r + \delta r_{ph} + r \cdot \delta C + v_{rq} + v_{rdes} + v_{rt} + v_{roth} \quad (16)$$

$$\tilde{z}_{\dot{r}} = \dot{r} + \delta \dot{r}_d + \dot{r} \cdot \delta C + \dot{r} \cdot \delta F + v_{\dot{r}q} + v_{\dot{r}des} + v_{\dot{r}t} + v_{\dot{r}oth} \quad (17)$$

where r and \dot{r} are the true range and range rate, respectively. SAR measurements of azimuth, denoted \tilde{z}_A , and elevation angle, denoted \tilde{z}_E , respectively, are given by

$$\tilde{z}_A = A + \delta A_{temp} + v_A \quad (18)$$

$$\tilde{z}_E = E + \delta E_{temp} + v_E \quad (19)$$

respectively, where A denotes the true azimuth angle and E denotes the true elevation angle. The GPS measurements of pseudo range, denoted \tilde{z}_{PR_i} , and delta range, denoted \tilde{z}_{DR_i} , for the i^{th} satellite are given by

$$\tilde{z}_{PR_i} = R_i + \delta SC_i + \delta TR_i + \delta ION_i + \delta RC_b + \delta PR_{res} + v_{cl} \quad (20)$$

$$\tilde{z}_{DR_i} = DR_i + \Delta T \cdot \delta RC_d + \Delta T \cdot A_x \cdot \delta a_x + \Delta T \cdot A_y \cdot \delta a_y + \Delta T \cdot A_z \cdot \delta a_z + \delta DR_{res} + v_{car} \quad (21)$$

where R_i and DR_i are the true range and delta range, respectively, and where A_x , A_y , and A_z are the body frame-

components of the aircraft acceleration.

Table 1: Stochastic models for SAR and GPS measurement errors.

Symbol	Description	Corr. Time	RMS Value
δc	Propagation speed error	bias	10 ppm
δf	Frequency error	bias	20 ppm
δr_{ph}	Range clock/phase error	bias	0.01 ft
δr_d	Range rate Doppler error	bias	0.001 ft/s
v_{rq}	Range quantization error	white	$\Delta r/\sqrt{2}$
v_{rdes}	Range designation error	white	$2\Delta r$
v_{rt}	Range timing error	white	$t_d \ddot{r}$
v_{roth}	Model for other range errors (e.g. multipath, edge of map, high maneuvers, small squint angle, etc.)	white	$\frac{\Delta r}{2}$
v_{rq}	Range rate quantization error	white	$\Delta \dot{r}/\sqrt{2}$
v_{rdes}	Range rate designation error	white	$2\Delta \dot{r}$
v_{rt}	Range rate timing error ^a	white	$t_d \ddot{r}$
v_{rm}	Model for other range rate errors (e.g. multipath, edge of map, high maneuvers, small squint angle, etc.)	white	$\frac{\Delta \dot{r}}{2}$
δA_{temp}	Azimuth angle temperature induced error.	bias	0.4 mr
δE_{temp}	Elevation angle temperature induced error.	bias	0.4 mr
v_A	Model for other azimuth angle errors (e.g. radome errors, flexure errors, thermal noise, quantization, etc.).	white	0.75 mr
v_E	Model for other elevation angle errors (e.g. radome errors, flexure errors, thermal noise, quantization, etc.).	white	0.70 mr
δSC_i	Satellite vehicle clock error for the i^{th} satellite.	bias	10.5 ft
δSV_{eb}	Ephemeris bias error for the i^{th} satellite.	-	6.6 ft
δSV_{ed}	Ephemeris drift error for the i^{th} satellite.	bias	0.0009 ft/s
δTR_i	Troposphere error for the i^{th} satellite.	1 hour	6 ft
δION_i	Ionosphere error for the i^{th} satellite.	2 hours	3.6 ft
δRC_b	Receiver clock bias.	-	90 ft
δRC_d	Receiver clock drift.	1.5 hours	9 ft/s
δa	Receiver clock g-sensitivity. $\delta a = [\delta a_x \ \delta a_y \ \delta a_z]^T$	bias	0.6 ft/s/g
v_{cl}	Code loop noise	white	1.5 ft
v_{car}	Carrier noise.	white	0.06 ft
δPR_{res}	Pseudo-range resolution error	0.75 hours	3 ft
δDR_{res}	Delta-range resolution error	0.75 hours	0.03 ft

6. FILTER ESTIMATES

The development that follows is based on a full order extended Kalman filter with states for all of the errors described in the previous section that are not modeled as white noise. The symbol “ $\hat{\cdot}$ ” is used over variable names

to denote the filter’s best estimate of the quantity in question.

The filter based estimate of aircraft position, denoted \hat{r}_a^n , and velocity, denoted \hat{v}_a^n , are given by the following

$$\hat{r}_a^n = \bar{r}_a^n - \delta \hat{r}_a^n, \quad (22)$$

$$\hat{v}_a^n = \bar{v}_a^n - \delta \hat{v}_a^n, \quad (23)$$

where $\delta \hat{r}_a^n$ and $\delta \hat{v}_a^n$ are the filter’s estimate of the INS indicated position error vector and velocity error vector, respectively. The filter based estimate of the body to navigation frame transformation, denoted \hat{C}_b^n , is given by

$$\hat{C}_b^n = [I + \hat{\Psi}] \bar{C}_b^n \quad (24)$$

where $\hat{\Psi}$ is the skew symmetric matrix of $\hat{\psi}$, the filter’s estimate of the INS indicated aircraft attitude error.

Similarly, the filter based estimate of the antenna to body frame transformation, denoted \hat{C}_a^b , is given by the following

$$\hat{C}_a^b = [I + \hat{B}] \bar{C}_a^b \quad (25)$$

where \hat{B} is the skew symmetric matrix of $\hat{\beta}$, the filter’s estimate of the indicated antenna attitude error.

The filter’s estimate of the target location is given by the following expression

$$\hat{r}_t^e = \bar{r}_t^e - \delta \hat{r}_t^e \quad (26)$$

where $\delta \hat{r}_t^e$ is the filter’s estimate of the indicated target location error.

Measurement Estimates

The Kalman filter’s best estimate of the SAR measurements of range and range rate are given by the following equations

$$\hat{z}_r = \hat{r} + \delta \hat{r}_{ph} + \hat{r} \cdot \delta \hat{C} \quad (27)$$

$$\hat{z}_r = \hat{r} + \delta \hat{r}_d + \hat{r} \cdot \delta \hat{C} + \hat{r} \cdot \delta \hat{F} \quad (28)$$

respectively. The filter’s estimate of true range and range rate are computed by

$$\hat{r} = |\hat{r}_t^n - \hat{r}_a^n| = |\hat{p}^n| \quad (29)$$

$$\hat{\dot{r}} = \left(\frac{-(\hat{p}^n)^T}{[(\hat{p}^n)^T \hat{p}^n]^{1/2}} \right) \hat{v}_a^n = -\hat{u}_p^n \hat{v}_a^n \quad (30)$$

where \hat{u}_p^n is the filter’s estimate of the unit LOS vector between the aircraft and the target.

The Kalman filter’s estimate of azimuth and elevation

angle measurements are given by

$$\hat{z}_A = \hat{A} + \delta \hat{A}_{temp} \quad (31)$$

$$\hat{z}_E = \hat{E} + \delta \hat{E}_{temp} \quad (32)$$

respectively, where \hat{A} is the filter's estimate of true azimuth angle and \hat{E} is the filter's estimate of true elevation angle. To compute \hat{A} and \hat{E} , we define the unit vectors

$$\hat{u}_{ay}^a \triangleq [0 \ 1 \ 0]^T \quad (33)$$

$$\hat{u}_{az}^a \triangleq [0 \ 0 \ 1]^T \quad (34)$$

which point in the antenna frame y and z directions, respectively. These vectors are expressed in navigation frame coordinates by applying the appropriate coordinate transformations.

$$\hat{u}_{ay}^n = \hat{C}_b^n \hat{C}_a^b \hat{u}_{ay}^a \quad (35)$$

$$\hat{u}_{az}^n = \hat{C}_b^n \hat{C}_a^b \hat{u}_{az}^a \quad (36)$$

Notice that \hat{u}_{ay}^n and \hat{u}_{az}^n are unit vectors. Consequently, their components are direction cosine angles (i.e. the cosine of the angles between the navigation frame coordinate axes and the line of sight vector). Hence, the filter's estimate of the true azimuth and elevation angles are given by the following

$$\hat{A} = \arccos \left((\hat{u}_{ay}^n)^T \hat{u}_{ay}^a \right), \quad (37)$$

$$\hat{E} = \arccos \left((\hat{u}_{az}^n)^T \hat{u}_{az}^a \right), \quad (38)$$

respectively.

The filter's estimate of the GPS measurements of pseudo-range and delta-range for the i^{th} satellite are given by

$$\hat{z}_{pR_i} = \hat{R}_i + \delta \hat{S}C_i + \delta \hat{T}R_i + \delta \hat{I}ON_i + \delta \hat{R}C_b + \delta \hat{P}R_{res} \quad (39)$$

$$\hat{z}_{DR_i} = \hat{D}R_i + \Delta T \cdot \delta \hat{R}C_d + \Delta T \cdot A_x \cdot \delta \hat{a}_x + \Delta T \cdot A_y \cdot \delta \hat{a}_y + \Delta T \cdot A_z \cdot \delta \hat{a}_z + \delta \hat{D}R_{res} \quad (40)$$

respectively. The filter's estimate of the true range, denoted \hat{R}_i , and delta-range, denoted $\hat{D}R_i$, are given by the following equations

$$\hat{R}_i = |r_s^a - r_d^a| + \delta S V_{eb_i} - \delta S V_{eb_s} \quad (41)$$

$$\hat{D}R_i(t_e) = \hat{P}R_i(t_e) - \hat{P}R_i(t_s) \quad (42)$$

where r_s^a is the true earth referenced satellite position, t_s is the start time for the Doppler integration period, and t_e is the end time for the Doppler period.

In Equation 42, the delta-range is obtained by differencing the filter's estimate of the pseudo-range measurement at the "start" and "end" times of the integration period. One possible method of performing this computation is to store the filter's estimate of the pseudo-range at the start of the integration period and difference this with the filter's estimate at the end of the integration period. However, this method exhibits several significant drawbacks. For example, if measurements are processed during the Doppler integration interval, then the previously stored pseudo-range estimate does not benefit from this new measurement. Also, the possible step changes in the filter's state estimate due to measurement updates make it very difficult to linearize the nonlinear measurement.

Hence, a better method is to back-propagate the filter's estimate of satellite ephemeris error and aircraft position error from the end time back to the start time of the Doppler integration interval. Equation 41 is then used to compute the start time pseudo-range measurement estimate from the filter's error state estimate obtained from back-propagation, the indicated aircraft position at the start time, and the satellite ephemeris position at the start time.

Under this scheme, the filter's estimate of the previous pseudo-range measurement is based on all available measurements at the end of the integration period. Also, the backpropagation process does not exhibit the step changes which are inherent in the filter's estimate during the forward propagation. Hence, linearization of Equation 42 becomes much easier. This back-propagation scheme was employed for the results shown in this paper.

7. LINEARIZATION

When designing an extended Kalman filter, linearized measurement equations are required. This section presents the linearized SAR and GPS measurement equations used in the extended Kalman filter design. The linearized measurement equations are obtained by computing a first order Taylor series approximation. For example, consider the following general non-linear measurement and its estimate

$$\tilde{z} = h_s(x_o, \delta x, \delta \hat{x}, t) + v_s, \quad (43)$$

$$\hat{z} = h_f(x_o, \delta x, \delta \hat{x}, t), \quad (44)$$

respectively, where h_s and h_f are non-linear functions, x_o denotes the true whole value state vector (e.g. aircraft position, velocity, and attitude), δx denotes the true error state vector, $\delta \hat{x}$ denotes the filter's estimate of the error

state vector, and v_s denotes white measurement noise. The first order Taylor series approximations of Equations 43 and 44 are given by the following

$$\tilde{z} \equiv z_o + \left. \frac{\partial h_s(x_o, \delta x, \hat{\delta x}, t)}{\partial (\delta x)} \right|_{\hat{x}_o, t} \delta x + \left. \frac{\partial h_s(x_o, \delta x, \hat{\delta x}, t)}{\partial (\delta \hat{x})} \right|_{\hat{x}_o, t} \delta \hat{x} + v_s \quad (45)$$

$$\hat{z} \equiv z_o + \left. \frac{\partial h_s(x_o, \delta x, \hat{\delta x}, t)}{\partial (\delta x)} \right|_{\hat{x}_o, t} \delta x + \left. \frac{\partial h_s(x_o, \delta x, \hat{\delta x}, t)}{\partial (\delta \hat{x})} \right|_{\hat{x}_o, t} \delta \hat{x} \quad (46)$$

where z_o is the true value of the measured quantity (e.g. true range) and \hat{x}_o is the filter's estimate of the whole valued state. Equations 45 and 46 may be expressed more compactly as

$$\tilde{z} \equiv z_o + H_{ss} \delta x + H_{sf} \delta \hat{x} + v_s \quad (47)$$

$$\hat{z} \equiv z_o + H_{fs} \delta x + H_{ff} \delta \hat{x} \quad (48)$$

The measurement residual, denoted Δz , is expressed as the difference between the measurement and the filter's estimate of the measurement, i.e.

$$\Delta z = \tilde{z} - \hat{z} \quad (49)$$

$$\equiv H_{ss} \delta x + H_{sf} \delta \hat{x} + v_s - H_{fs} \delta x - H_{ff} \delta \hat{x} \quad (50)$$

$$\equiv (H_{ss} - H_{fs}) \delta x - (H_{ff} - H_{sf}) \delta \hat{x} + v_s \quad (51)$$

$$\equiv H_s \delta x - H_f \delta \hat{x} + v_s \quad (52)$$

where H_s is the "system observation matrix" and H_f is the "filter observation matrix". The filter observation matrix is used to compute the filter gain and to perform the covariance update in an extended Kalman filter. The true measurement residual given by Equation 49 is used along with the filter gain to perform state updates. This is different than a linearized Kalman filter. The system observation matrix is needed only when performing covariance analysis.

For the results presented in this paper, the filter observation matrices for SAR measurements are similar to those presented in [8,9]. The components which make up the filter observation matrix for both SAR and GPS measurements are summarized in Tables 2, 3, and 4. The entries in these table are the elements of matrix H_f which multiply the given filter state. All components not shown in the tables are zero.

$$\hat{L} = -\frac{1}{\hat{r}} [I - \hat{u}_p^n (\hat{u}_p^n)^t] \quad (53)$$

Table 2: SAR range and range rate measurement matrix (non-zero components of filter observation matrix).

State	Range Measurement - \hat{z}_r	Range Rate Measurement - \hat{z}_r
δr_a^n	$(1 + \delta \hat{C}) (\hat{u}_p^n)^t$	$(1 + \delta \hat{C} + \delta \hat{F}) (\hat{u}_p^n)^t \hat{L}$
δv_a^n	0	$(1 + \delta \hat{C} + \delta \hat{F}) (\hat{u}_p^n)^t$
δr_f^n	$-(1 + \delta \hat{C}) (\hat{u}_p^n)^t \hat{C}_e^n$	$-(1 + \delta \hat{C} + \delta \hat{F}) (\hat{u}_p^n)^t \hat{L} \hat{C}_e^n$
$\delta \hat{C}$	\hat{r}	\hat{r}
$\delta \hat{F}$	0	\hat{r}
δr_{ph}^n	1	0
δr_d^h	0	1

Table 3: SAR azimuth and elevation angle measurement matrix (non-zero components of filter observation matrix).

State	Azimuth Angle - \hat{z}_A	Elevation Angle - \hat{z}_E
δr_a^n	$(\nabla \hat{A}^n)^t$	$(\nabla \hat{E}^n)^t$
$\hat{\psi}$	$\hat{r} (\nabla \hat{A}^n)^t (\hat{u}_p^n)^*$	$\hat{r} (\nabla \hat{E}^n)^t (\hat{u}_p^n)^*$
δr_f^n	$-(\nabla \hat{A}^n)^t \hat{C}_e^n$	$-(\nabla \hat{E}^n)^t \hat{C}_e^n$
$\hat{\beta}$	$\hat{r} (\nabla \hat{A}^n)^t (\hat{u}_p^n)^* \hat{C}_e^n$	$\hat{r} (\nabla \hat{E}^n)^t (\hat{u}_p^n)^* \hat{C}_e^n$
$\delta \hat{A}_{temp}$	1	0
$\delta \hat{E}_{temp}$	0	1

Superscript * on a vector denotes the skew symmetric matrix form of the vector.

$$(\nabla \hat{A}^n)^t = -\frac{(\hat{u}_{ay}^n)^t}{\hat{r} \sin(A)} [I - \hat{u}_p^n (\hat{u}_p^n)^t] \quad (54)$$

$$(\nabla \hat{E}^n)^t = -\frac{(\hat{u}_{az}^n)^t}{\hat{r} \sin(A)} [I - \hat{u}_p^n (\hat{u}_p^n)^t] \quad (55)$$

$$\Delta \hat{u}_p^n(t_e) = \hat{u}_p^n(t_e) - \hat{u}_p^n(t_s) \quad (56)$$

8. SIMULATION RESULTS

The targeting analysis consists of performing both relative and absolute SAR targeting on a "target of opportunity" (i.e. a target whose location is unknown *a priori*). As is shown, the type of navigation aiding performed has a considerable impact on the targeting accuracy.

Table 4: GPS pseudo-range and delta-range measurement matrix (non-zero components of filter observation matrix).

State	Pseudo-range - \hat{z}_{PR}	Delta-range - \hat{z}_{DR}
$\delta \hat{a}_a^n$	$(\hat{u}_p^n)'$	$(\Delta \hat{u}_p^n(t_s))'$
$\delta \hat{v}_a^n$	0	$\Delta T \cdot (\hat{u}_p^n)'$
$\delta \hat{S}C$	1	0
$\delta \hat{T}R$	1	0
$\delta \hat{I}O\hat{N}$	1	0
$\delta \hat{S}V_{eb}$	-1	0
$\delta \hat{S}V_{ed}$	0	$-\Delta T$
$\delta \hat{R}C_b$	1	0
$\delta \hat{P}R_{res}$	1	0
$\delta \hat{R}C_d$	0	ΔT
$\delta \hat{a}_x$	0	$\Delta T \cdot A_x$
$\delta \hat{a}_y$	0	$\Delta T \cdot A_y$
$\delta \hat{a}_z$	0	$\Delta T \cdot A_z$
$\delta \hat{D}R_{res}$	0	1

The simulated flight profile consists of a simple straight and level flight with an aircraft velocity of 750 ft/s at an altitude of 10,000 ft. During the flight, the aircraft passes near one surveyed landmark for possible navigation updates. Also, in the latter portion of the flight the aircraft passes near a “target of opportunity” whose relative and absolute coordinates are obtained via SAR measurements.

The initial conditions for all INS states were obtained using the filter’s covariance matrix resulting from an 8 minute simulated gyro-compass alignment. This alignment process was implemented by processing zero velocity measurements in the full order, extended Kalman filter (i.e. the aircraft is assumed stationary). The initial conditions for all other errors are based on the RMS values presented in previous sections. The filter’s estimate was feed back to the system after every measurement update. Due to the fact that the truth model and the filter model are the same, this so called “discrete time feedback” is implemented by the following equations

$$\delta \mathbf{x}(t^+) = \delta \mathbf{x}(t^-) - \delta \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t^-), \quad (57)$$

$$\delta \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t^+) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (58)$$

In Figure 3, GPS pseudo-range measurements are processed on 1 sec intervals and delta-range measurements are processed on 0.15 sec intervals. The results show that

Figure 3: Combined SAR and GPS aiding (aircraft north position and velocity error).

GPS aiding can maintain aircraft position error to about 7 feet RMS and velocity error to about 0.05 ft/s RMS. Combined SAR and GPS aiding provides little improvement over the GPS only case but does provide information about the SAR measurement errors. Consequently, the advantages of the combined SAR and GPS aiding becomes more clear in the targeting analysis results presented.

The SAR targeting analysis presented here contains results for both relative and absolute targeting. Relative targeting is performed by computing the location of the target from a single set of SAR measurements and the INS indicated velocity. Absolute targeting is implemented by two different possible methods. The first method is performed by computing the absolute target location from the relative target location and the INS indicated aircraft position. The second method is performed by processing the SAR measurements in the extended Kalman Filter to obtain a good estimate of the indicated target location error. This method is similar to that proposed by Gibbs *et al* in [10].

The relative and absolute targeting errors resulting from the computation methods described above are shown in Figure 4. Here the targeting performance is compared for each of the different types of navigation aiding.

As expected, the results show that, in general, relative targeting is more accurate than absolute targeting. Also, due to the smaller aircraft position and velocity error, the targeting error for GPS aided navigation is smaller than the SAR aided case. Finally, it is important to note that the results for the combined SAR and GPS aiding shows a significant improvement over the GPS only case.

Figure 4: Relative and absolute SAR targeting error. The results shown here are based on computing the location from SAR measurements and the INS indicated aircraft position.

For the combined GPS and SAR aiding scenario, results show that the Kalman filter method exhibits better performance over the computed method. This improvement is achieved because the aircraft position error is much smaller (due to GPS aiding) than the initial indicated targeting location error. Research with other scenarios such as SAR aiding only, has shown little or no improvement by use of the Kalman filter method. The Kalman filter method of SAR targeting can be viewed as the reciprocal to the navigation aiding. In SAR navigation aiding good knowledge of the landmark's location is needed. Likewise, for the Kalman filter method of SAR targeting, good knowledge of the aircraft position is needed.

9. CONCLUSIONS

This paper illustrates the design and optimal performance of an integrated INS, GPS, and SAR. The benign flight profiles and other simulation conditions were purposely chosen such that they would minimize most system errors. Therefore, the presented analysis illustrates the theoretical best performance available from such a system.

The results presented in this paper indicate a theoretical possibility of obtaining both aircraft and target position with a CEP less than 10 feet. This level of performance may be possible if both SAR and GPS measurements are processed in an extended Kalman filter. However, the result also show that if GPS is not employed, then little improvement in the targeting accuracy is obtained by processing the SAR measurement in a Kalman filter.

Future work in this area will focus on the sensitivity of individual errors on the overall system accuracy. A sensitivity analysis will provide a indication of the states that should be removed from the Kalman filter design (i.e. an error state that has little influence on the overall system accuracy can be removed from the Kalman filter model). The results presented here can be used as the baseline for comparison of any reduced order Kalman filter designs.

10. REFERENCES

- [1] P. Maybeck, *Stochastic Models, Estimation, and Control Volume 1*, San Diego, California: Academic Press, Inc., 1979.
- [2] J. C. Nelander and A. C. Kenton and J. A. Wright, "Performance sensitivities of position and velocity determination using SAR vision guidance updates," *Proceedings of the Southeastcon Conference on Energy and Information Technologies in the Southeast*, pp. 90-94, Columbia, South Carolina, April 1989.
- [3] A. C. Kenton and J. A. Wright and J. C. Nelander, "Vision guidance update: synthetic aperture radar (SAR) multiple image exploitation for position and velocity determination," *SPIE Millimeter Wave and Synthetic Aperture Radar*, vol. 1101, pp. 158-169, 1989.
- [4] W. G. Heller, "Models for aided inertial navigation system sensor errors," Tech. Rep. TR-312-3, The Analytic Sciences Corporation, Reading, Mass., February 1975.
- [5] J. Layne, "Integrated synthetic aperture radar and navigation systems for targeting applications," Tech Memo, Wright Laboratory (AFMC), Wright Patterson AFB, Ohio, Oct. 1993.
- [6] S. Burgett, "Target location in WGS-84 coordinates using synthetic aperture radar," *ION Proceedings of the 49th Annual Meeting*, pp 57-65, Cambridge, Massachusetts, June 1993.
- [7] Military Avionics Division, "Honeywell H423 performance accuracy (truth model-error budget) analysis," Tech. Rep. 1184-1012, Honeywell, Clearwater, Florida, November 1984.
- [8] S. H. Musick, "Radar measurements and measurement matrices," Tech. Rep. AFAL-TM-76-48, Wright Laboratory (AFMC), Wright Patterson AFB, Ohio, May 1976.
- [9] D. J. Schmidt, "Error analysis of an air-to-surface missile with a synthetic aperture radar seeker," *NAECON*, pp 363-370, Dayton, Ohio, May 1981.
- [10] R. Gibbs, M. Bottkol and T. Owens, "Flight demonstration of image fix-taking with SAR," *ION Proceedings of the 49th Annual Meeting*, pp 51-55, Cambridge, Massachusetts, June 1993.